

IDENTIFICATION, DIVERSITY AND POPULATION STRUCTURE OF *PHYTOPHTHORA* INFECTING FORESTRY IN EUROPE

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An increasing number of reports of new emerging diseases affecting forest trees caused by several *Phytophthora* spp. indicate that this pathogen pose considerable risks to natural ecosystems. The knowledge of the genus *Phytophthora* is still limited as shown by the high number of new species that are being identified in recent years. In addition, the existing high risk of emergence of new species through hybridization indicates that the knowledge of the taxonomy and biology of the genus is incomplete. The objective of this work was the identification and characterization of new species of *Phytophthora* populations damaging broadleaf and conifer trees based on the use of next generation sequencing (NGS) of PCR amplicons of ITS rRNA. However, since some *Phytophthora* species are closely related and cannot be discriminated based on their ITS sequence we also explored the use of the cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) as a barcode gene. PCR products were amplified from soil samples collected from 104 locations in England, Scotland and Wales from 'disturbed' sites (sites frequently visited by the public, with recent and new plantings, link to nurseries; 83 locations sampled in 9 sites) and from more 'natural' forest and woodland sites (with little disturbance or management; 51 locations sampled in 5 sites). *Phytophthora* was detected in all disturbed and undisturbed sites and in more than 80% of all samples when primers targeting the COI region were used and in a slight lower number when primers targeting the ITS were used. NGS analyses of the ITS region revealed the presence of other oomycetes (7,9% of sequences) in the soil samples apart from *Phytophthora* spp., while those using the COI region revealed lower specificity as compared to ITS since amplified several sequences from diatoms, algi, fungi, an unidentified insect, and several oomycetes different from *Phytophthora*. Results from NGS analysis of ITS sequences identified 36 *Phytophthora* species/phylotypes, whereas those using the COI region identified 28 species/phylotypes, and the combination of both allowed the detection of up to 39 *Phytophthora* spp.. The taxonomy assignation of ZOTUs was obtained after comparing the NGS data with different curated *Phytophthora* databases. We found that the taxonomic assignation of some ZOTUs to a specific *Phytophthora* species varied with the database used, which makes it necessary to have a common curate database to avoid misidentifications, and also to isolate in parallel some of those problematic specimens to be able to confirm their species identity.